

An Empirical Study of Barriers to Digital Financial Inclusion with the Mediating Effect of Awareness Among People

ELINA KANUNGO, DEVIKA, SARAT KUMAR SAMANTARAY AND ASHOK AGRAWAL

Abstract : *There are various factors responsible for restraining the growth of digital financial inclusion in India. The present paper examines the mediating effects of awareness of people on the relationship between Digital Financial Inclusion (DFI) and the barriers affecting it. For achieving the objectives of this study, a research model was developed to test the mediating effect of awareness on the relationship between different factors acting as barriers to DFI and DFI. The data for the study is collected from 776 respondents residing in the district of Puri, Odisha, India by framing a structured questionnaire, and structural equation modeling in partial least square (PLS) combined with bootstrap was applied to analyze and test the hypotheses of this study. Awareness as a mediator affects the relationship between the barrier and the DFI significantly. Awareness of operations of the digital platform, control, and redressal mechanism is of paramount importance as people are using financial services digitally. Moreover, the restraining barriers affect the DFI more in case of a lack of awareness among the users of digital services.*

Keywords : Awareness, Barriers, Bootstrap, Digital Financial Inclusion, Mediator, PLS-SEM

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1. Introduction

The usage of digital technology has been proven to be an effective means for the attainment of the objective of financial inclusion. In the present digital age, people are encouraged to avail of financial services and perform other financial transactions by using the digital platform. **Zetzsche et al. (2019)** highlighted that according to the Global Partnership for Financial Inclusion (GPMI), Digital Financial Inclusion (DFI) consists of the use of the digital medium to reach the underserved population with a wide array of financial services at an affordable cost. They further stated that mobile money (Use of e-money on a mobile phone) and M-Pesa in Kenya has signified how innovations are facilitating financial inclusion. For using the virtual platform, it is essential that the user is digitally and financially literate. **Shen et al. (2020)** have identified four elements of DFI namely the Availability or access to digital financial products, Affordability, Financial literacy, and Ability to use digital products. **Svitlana et al. (2019)** concluded that the low level of public awareness of using innovative products and services is one of the reasons behind the low inclusion of financial services. To attain digital financial inclusiveness, there needs to have financial inclusion digitally that is people must be able to avail of financial services through digital platforms. But not all are able to use this platform. There are certain conditions or factors which restrain people to use digital platforms.

2. Review of Literature

The development of Digital Financial Inclusion (DFI) leads to improvement in the coverage of financial services, **Yang & Zhang (2020)**. **Dahlman et al. (2016)** believed that the digitalization of the economy fosters growth and productivity and paves the way for inclusive development. A study by **Mahmood et al. (2021)** in China revealed that DFI increases regional economic growth as it facilitates ease of access to financial services with affordability. **Ozili (2018)** in his study concluded that digital finance through Fintech providers has positively affected financial inclusion in emerging and advanced economies. **Shen, Hueng & Hu (2020)** stated in their research that digital technology has emerged as an ideal medium to reach many customers across a wide territory. They further concluded that financial literacy and usage of digital financial products are highly important for increasing financial inclusion in China. **Bathula & Gupta (2021)** have defined the DFI in terms of the use of DFS namely debit cards, credit cards, etc in the past 1 year and ownership of these instruments along with owning a mobile phone.

Morgan et al. (2019) stated that financial technology (fintech), i.e., using software, applications, and digital platforms to deliver financial services to consumers and businesses through digital devices such as smartphones, has emerged as an eminent tool for promoting access to financial services by underserved populations. **Morgan & Trinh (2019)** stated categories of financial services like e-commerce, mobile banking, mobile wallets, digital currency, etc., offered through digital platforms by fintech firms. The use of Debit and credit cards society by providing the option of digital payment is contributing to the growth of a cashless economy, **Kijkasiwat & Chancharat (2022)**. **Mhlanga (2020)** revealed the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming financial inclusion which enables vulnerable groups of women, youth, and small businesses to avail the financial services digitally. **Alameda (2020); Bill & Melinda (2019)** identified that mobile phone is not the only instrument for facilitating the DFI but instruments like payment cards can also be linked to a device like a Point of Sale (PoS) for making a financial transaction. For the purpose of taking proper financial decisions and attaining individual financial well-being, an individual must possess the financial awareness, knowledge, skills, attitude, and behaviors required (**OECD 2018**). In the present study, DFI is measured by using constructs like ownership and DFS.

Pazarbasioglu et al. (2020), stated “In developing economies, about two-thirds of adults without financial services cite having too little money as a barrier to account ownership, and roughly one-quarter say accounts are too expensive. In Latin America and the Caribbean, roughly half of the adults without financial services say accounts are too expensive. With lower marginal and fixed costs, DFS can be more cheaply delivered. This also allows for transaction-based pricing, which can be more suitable for the poor.” They further came up with one of the findings that successful use of the DFS needs that people must have awareness and knowledge of the digital financial products and services, financial risks, financial control mechanism, and consumer redressal mechanism.

Liew et al. (2020) observed in their research that knowledge about digital financial risks and the knowledge of consumer rights and procedures of redressal have the lowest mean score. This indicates that there is a low level of awareness of FinTech products and services among people.

Azeez & Akhtar (2021) has highlighted Digital Financial Awareness (DFA) as one of the important elements of Digital Financial Literacy (DFL). **Lyons & Hanna (2021)**, and **Kass et al (2022)** highlighted that awareness of positive financial attitudes and behavior is equally important for digital financial inclusion. They

emphasized the importance of a positive financial attitude on the part of digital users. The government of India has taken a foot forward to make the economy not only financially inclusive but digitally financially inclusive through its 'Digital India' initiatives. The government is encouraging its people to adopt digital tools for availing of financial services. In India, a broader Digital India revolution catalyzed by PMJDY, India Stack, e-KYC, and UPI brought a paradigm shift in the way financial services are availed by consumers, **NITI Aayog Report (2022)**. The Reserve Bank of India (RBI) with the intention of building a Fintech ecosystem in India has promoted a Unified Payment Interface (UPI), digital payments, P2P, etc. It has also granted licenses to 11 Fintech entities for the establishment of payment banks **Kandpal & Mehrotra, (2019)**. **Lontchi et al. (2022)** stated that the significance can be assessed using p-value, t-statistics, and beta value ($\hat{\alpha}$).

Barik & Sharma (2019) concluded that despite the high growth of digital transactions, digital usage is not the same in people of different groups. Digital usage among women, rural people, elderly people, and less educated people is much less than among other groups of people. **Tiwari et al. (2019)** identified illiteracy, innumeracy, and unfamiliarity with technology as barriers to the use of digital products. **Bagla & Sancheti, (2018)** stated that the satisfaction level of customers using the digital platform is affected by factors like security, user-friendly interface, transaction cost, etc, to name a few. These factors pose challenges to the sustainability of digital products and hence need attention for their removal or proper solution.

3. Methodology

3.1. Sample and Collection of Data

The present study has made a valuable effort in highlighting the barriers affecting the DFI. The sample has been selected using a convenient sampling method based on literacy rates from 3 urban and 4 rural places in the district of Puri, Odisha, India. The data for the study has been collected from primary as well as secondary sources. Secondary sources include publications in different journals, magazines, websites, etc. Primary data has been collected using a structured questionnaire. The data is coded in binary (0-No, 1- Yes). Questions pertaining to barriers are collected using 5 point Likert scale where 5 denoted strongly agree and 1 as Strongly disagree.

3.2. Tools for Data Analysis

The statistical tool used to examine the hypothetical model developed in the study is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) using Smart-PLS, **Ringle (2022)**. Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) in partial least square (PLS) combined with bootstrap was applied to analyze the data collected from 776 respondents residing in the district of Puri, Odisha, India.

3.3. Measurement of Variables

The constructs in the study namely DFS, Ownership, Awareness, and Barriers are represented by 4, 3, 4, and 12 items each respectively. DFS, purpose, and awareness are reflective in nature and Ownership is a formative construct. Table 1 gives a vivid view of the items of each construct. The theoretical and empirical evidence given in the study has led to hypothesize the following :

H1 : Awareness has a significant relationship with DFS.

H2 : Awareness has a significant relationship with ownership.

H3 : Barriers to using the digital platform have a significant and negative relationship with DFS.

H4 : Barriers to using the digital platform have a significant and negative relationship with ownership.

H5 : Awareness mediates significantly the relationship between DFI and Barriers to using digital products.

H6 : Awareness mediates significantly the relationship between ownership and Barriers to using digital products.

4. Results and Discussion

Chin (2010) and Hair et al. (2017) presented a two-step process for the analysis of data using PLS-SEM. The two-way process includes the assessment of the measurement model representing the relationship between latent constructs and observed indicators and the assessment of the structural model which shows the relationship between latent constructs. The former is called the outer model and the latter is the inner model **Ringle et al. (2022)**.

4.1. Constructing Measurement Model

The measurement model is constructed and composite reliability, convergent and discriminant validities of the latent variables are tested by taking the factor loadings into account. Cronbach's alpha is used to measure the composite reliability. Table 2 reflects the values that are greater than the recommended value of 0.70 (Nunnally (1978), Bagozzi and Yi (1988), Cronbach (1971)).

Table-1 : Constructs' Indicators

CONSTRUCT	MEASUREMENT	INDICATORS
Barriers	Reflective	B1: While using digital payment systems, there is anxiousness about the loss of connection
		B2: Minor mistakes lead to financial losses while using a digital payment system.
		B3: There is doubt about wrongly tapping the bill information while using digital payment systems
		B4: There is insecurity while using digital payment systems regarding the loss of PIN codes which might reach the wrong hands
		B5: There is fear while using digital payment systems, as the third party might get access to my account information
		B6: The procedure of using a digital platform is complex
		B7: There are difficulties in managing and remembering passwords while using digital payment systems
		B8: There is a lack of relevant knowledge to use digital products while using digital payment systems
		B9: Digital payment systems cannot be used for every purpose.
		B10: The redressal mechanism is not effective while using digital payment systems.
		B11: The redressal mechanism is too complex to understand while using digital payment systems.
		B12: There is a lack of adequate information about consumer rights and laws related to digital payment systems.

(Contd...)

Awareness	Reflective	Awareness of digital risks like Phishing, hacking, etc - AW-1
		Knowledge of financial products and services offered digitally- AW 2
		Knowledge of consumer rights- AW 3
		Knowledge of consumer redressal mechanism- AW 4
Ownership	Formative	Ownership of Debit card- Own 1
		Ownership of Credit card- Own 2
		Ownership of digital money account- Own 3
DFS	Reflective	Usage of a Debit card in the past 12 months- DFS 1
		Usage of Credit card in the past 12 months- DFS 2
		Usage of UPI/PPI/e-wallets in the past 12 months- DFS 3
		Usage of electronic payment systems like IMPS/ECS/NEFT in the past 12 months- DFS 4

Source : Compilation from the survey.

TABLE-2 : Reliability and Validity

Construct Reliability and Validity				
	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
AWARENESS	0.776	0.778	0.857	0.601
BARRIERS	0.979	0.980	0.981	0.814
DFS	0.837	0.845	0.891	0.672

Source : Smart PLS Output.

The outer loadings of the items indicating constructs access, barriers, DFI, DMP, and FL are statistically significant (at p-value = 0 .000). The research instrument establishes acceptable indicator reliability. Internal consistency reliability is also established through the alpha values of Cronbach alpha, **Straub, (1989)**, and Composite reliability tests **Gefen et al. (2000)**. The convergent validity is measured through the values of Average variance extracted (AVE). In the present study, the AVE of each construct exceeded 0.5 thereby indicating the establishment of the convergent validity for the constructs, **Kim, Gupta, & Koh (2011)**. The

construct of Ownership is formative in nature, so the reliability and validity are assured by the VIF values (Reflected in Table 4). All the indicators of constructs have factor loadings above the threshold of 0.70. **Hair et al. (2019)**. Though Ownership 2 has a loading of 0.460, it is explaining the construct significantly. The measurement of discriminant validity is done by using the Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) **Sinkovics (2009)**, **Hair et al. (2012)**, **Hanafiah (2020)**. The results of the measurement model indicate that the internal consistency reliability and convergent validity of the constructs are satisfactory.

4.2. Construction of Structural Model

The predictive relevance and effect size is determined after constructing the structural model (**Hair et al., 2016**). Consequently, a structural model through PLS-SEM bootstrap was constructed to study the impact of barriers to using the digital platform on DFS and ownership. The bootstrapping result indicates that barriers have a negative and significant impact on DFS and Ownership. Awareness as a construct mediates the relationship between ownership and barriers, and DFS and barriers. It is observed from the result that there are direct as well as specific indirect effects of awareness on both ownership and DFS. So, complementary mediation is observed in the model, **Lontchi et al. (2022)**.

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Source : Smart PLS Output.

Table-4 : VIF Values

VIF	
OWN_1	1.293
OWN_2	1.055
OWN_3	1.331

Source: Smart PLS Output.

Table-5 : Factor Loadings of the Kndicators

Indicators	AWARENESS	BARRIERS	DFS	OWN
AWARE1	0.721			
AWARE2	0.826			
AWARE3	0.842			
AWARE4	0.702			
B1		0.902		
B10		0.946		
B11		0.952		
B12		0.944		
B2		0.923		
B3		0.924		
B4		0.955		
B5		0.802		
B6		0.797		
B7		0.758		
B8		0.946		
B9		0.949		
DFS_1			0.815	
DFS_2			0.785	
DFS_3			0.872	
DFS_4			0.805	
OWN_1				0.780
OWN_2				0.460
OWN_3				0.874

Source : Smart PLS Output.

A 43.2% variance in the DFS is explained by Awareness, Ownership, and the barriers to using the digital platform variance. A 48.9% in Ownership is explained by Awareness, DFS, and the barriers to using the digital platform. **Chin (2010) concluded that** the R^2 value of 0.67 is substantial, 0.33 is moderate and 0.19 is considered weak. The result of the research shows an R^2 value above 0.33 and

hence the model suggested is moderate. **Hair et al., (2017) and Kijkasiwat & Chancharat (2022) highlighted** that the predictive relevance of the model can be measured through Stone-Geisser's Q Square reflecting a value greater than zero to have predictive relevance, The Q Square values obtained after cross-validated redundancy for the endogenous construct are greater than zero (0.267, 0.229, and 0.214 for awareness, DFS, and ownership respectively).

Table-6 : Results of Outer Weights

Indicators	Weights
B1 <- BARRIERS	0.094
B2 <- BARRIERS	0.108
B3 <- BARRIERS	0.082
B4 <- BARRIERS	0.103
B5<- BARRIERS	0.096
B6 <- BARRIERS	0.092
B7 <- BARRIERS	0.090
B8 <- BARRIERS	0.090
B9 <- BARRIERS	0.090
B10 <- BARRIERS	0.089
B11<- BARRIERS	0.087
B12<- BARRIERS	0.090

Table-7 : Results of Hypotheses Testing

	Relationship	β Value	S.D	T-Stats	*p values	Decision Supported
AWARENESS->DFS	Direct	0.388	0.032	12.290	0.000	Yes H1
AWARENESS->OWN	Direct	0.398	0.028	14.220	0.000	Yes H2
BARRIER->AWARENESS->OWN	Indirect	-0.115	0.009	12.130	0.000	Yes H5
BARRIER->AWARENESS->DFS	Indirect	-0.112	0.010	11.134	0.000	Yes H6
BARRIERS->DFS->	Direct	-0.147	0.016	9.478	0.000	Yes H3
BARRIERS->OWN	Direct	-0.111	0.013	8.274	0.000	Yes H4

*Source: Smart PLS Output, *Significant at 0.05 level based on 5000 bootstraps.*

Figure-1 : Proposed Structural Model

5. Major Findings

1. Attainment of the goal of digital financial inclusion is affected by digital financial literacy and barriers that come up in the way of people using the digital platform. The relationships between the constructs are assessed using 5000 bootstraps. The bootstrap result in Table 7 highlights the relationship between different constructs. It is observed that awareness has a significant, positive, and direct impact on DFS and ownership. Awareness of people is essential for owning a financial instrument and using different DFS. This leads to acceptance of H1 and H2 and leads to a finding that when people are aware of various financial services offered digitally, the consumer rights as a consumer of a digital platform, the risk associated with virtual and digital transactions, and the mechanism of redressal, they would use more digital financial products and services and would have ownership of various digital instruments like bank cards and with digital money providers like e-wallets, etc.
2. Barriers to using the digital platform also have a significant, negative, and direct impact on DFS and ownership respectively. This leads us to acceptance of H3 and H4 and to another finding that a well-aware person might have

restricted use of the digital platform if he faces certain challenges or difficulties in using the platform. There are certain factors identified as barriers to use the of digital products. Table 1 reflects the factors that act as barriers and Table 6 indicated the weights.

3. Minor mistakes lead to huge financial losses while using a digital payment system (B2) has a higher weight (0.108) of all the indicators and doubt about wrongly tapping the bill information while using digital payment systems (B3) has the least weight (0.082). People who are not adequately aware of the Digital Platform are quite skeptical while using it. It was observed during the study that people of different educational backgrounds and varied occupation uses digital products by taking the help of their friends and family members. They do so because they fear losing a huge sum of money due to a minor or negligible loss.
4. The direct and positive impact of these factors on DFS and ownership states that when people are affected by the mentioned factors, their ownership and usage of DFS are affected. The more the barriers the less they prefer to own and use the digital financial products.
5. It is observed from the result of Bootstrap that awareness mediates the relationship between barriers, DFS, and ownership. The mediation found is complementary in nature, **Lontchi et al. (2022)**. A low level of awareness leads to barriers affecting the DFS and ownership negatively and significantly. Awareness affects DFI both directly and indirectly and H5 and H6 are accepted.

6. Conclusion

The study set out to investigate the factors affecting DFI in the district of Puri, Odisha, India. The identified factors constituting the barriers will help to improve the level of digital usage and penetration in the place of research. Awareness among the users is found to be a factor of paramount importance. The level of awareness affects the DFS and ownership of digital financial products. A positive and significant relationship is observed between DFI (DFS and ownership) and awareness among the people. Some factors are identified as barriers that have a negative and significant impact on DFS and Ownership. These identified barriers are to be removed or handled properly to minimize their negative impact on digital inclusion. It is the responsibility of the policymakers to ensure that awareness programs can be conducted for making people aware of various digital

financial products, and their methods of operation, redressal, control mechanism, etc, so that the difficulties faced by them can be reduced. The present study is going to give insight into the current scenario of digital inclusion to the advocates of DFI and promoters of digital financial products. People must be encouraged for using digital products by removing the constraints that restrain them from adopting the digital platform. The authorities need to give importance to increasing the awareness levels of people to facilitate their use of the DFS. Conducting more numbers of financial awareness programs by either banks or different other authorities can reduce ignorance among people related to digital financial transactions. A person who is well- aware can handle his digital transactions with confidence. The research findings can throw light on framing strategies for eradicating the barriers and improving awareness among people for facilitating more digital financial inclusion.

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